

International Experience in Vocational Training Quality and Lessons for Vietnam

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Abstract:

The article has summarized the theoretical basis of training, training quality. Since then, we have conducted experience analysis to improve the quality of Chinese training because Vietnamese culture has many similarities with Chinese culture. Next, we analyze the situation of improving vocational training quality in Germany and Switzerland, two countries with developed education. Finally, we offer recommendations, lessons and solutions to improve the quality of vocational training in Vietnam.

Keywords: Vocational Training

1. Introduction

In 2015, when the ASEAN economic community is established, workers in ASEAN countries will be free to move in the region. This gives Vietnamese workers many opportunities but also challenges.

The quality of training is the result of the training process reflected in the characteristics of the quality, personality value and labor force value or the professional capacity of graduates corresponding to the goals and programs. training in specific industries "(Tran Khanh Duc - Institute of Educational Development Research). In the field of training, the quality of training is characterized by the product " Human labor ", which can be understood as the outcome (outcome) of the training process and is expressed in detail in the qualities, personality values and labor force values or the professional competence of the graduates, corresponding to the training objectives of the graduates. each training sector in the university training system, with the requirements to meet the labor needs of the labor market g) The notion that the quality of higher education does not only depend on the outcome of the training process in the school but also must take into account the suitability and adaptability of graduates to the labor market as the employment rate graduate, competency in specific positions, etc. However, it should be emphasized that the quality of training must first be the result of the training process and be expressed in the activities of graduate.

Improving the quality of training is to make the products of high-value training process reflected by deep knowledge, good skills and professional skills to meet the increasing demands of society. In particular, improving the quality of vocational training to form true capacity within the employees themselves is becoming an urgent issue in the current period. In the human resource development strategy, vocational training is always considered a key issue to create a skilled workforce with professional knowledge, skills and career attitudes appropriate to the requirements. demand for socio-economic development, to meet the economic structure change, to meet the needs of labor restructuring.

Over the past years, Vietnam's vocational training has made many achievements but also exposed limitations and shortcomings, failing to meet the requirements of the world of work, the gap between training and occupation is still large. . Schools only focus on perfecting hard skills for learners in which soft skills are not focused; The training program is not reasonable, still heavy in theory, light in practice (in some specialized subjects, the rate of theory accounts for 70% of the number of lectures, the practice makes up about 30% of the number of periods). graduates lack practical working skills, have not caught up and become familiar with the work of enterprises. The rate of students having a job is not high, in which most of them are not in the right training majors but must be in the wrong fields. Businesses who receive HSSV about work have to carry out retraining or additional training of practical skills from 3 to 6 months to meet the job requirements, adapt to the new environment and style. new work.

2. Literature review

2.1. Educate

According to the dictionary "Encyclopedia of Vietnam", training is the process of affecting a person in order to make him or her comprehend and grasp knowledge, skills, techniques ... systematically to prepare him to adapt to life and the ability to receive a certain division of labor, his contribution to the socio-economic development, maintenance and development of human civilization.

According to Tran Khanh Duc, 2004, training is a purposeful, organized process of activities in order to systematically formulate the knowledge, skills, and attitudes to improve personality for each individual, creating The premise can go into practice, be productive and effective.

According to Le Duc Ngoc, 2005, training is understood as a learning activity in order for employees to be able to more effectively carry out their functions and duties. In particular, training involves acquiring special knowledge and skills, in order to perform specific tasks more perfectly.

According to the Law on Vocational Education, 2014 "Vocational training is a teaching and learning activity aimed at equipping students with the knowledge, skills and career attitudes necessary to find jobs or to create jobs themselves later. when completing a course or to improve a career level "

The nature of "training" is the teaching of practical skills, career skills or knowledge related to a specific field, with the goal of helping learners acquire and master knowledge systematically. system, creating a premise for learners to adapt to life and the ability to take on a certain job. The concept of training has a narrower meaning than the concept of education. Usually, training refers to the later stage, when a person has reached a certain age, there is a certain level. There are many types of training: basic and intensive training, professional and vocational training, retraining, distance training, self-training ...

2.2. Education quality

Quality is always a matter of great concern and striving to improve training quality has always been considered the most important task of all training institutions in general and vocational training institutions in particular. Currently, there are many different interpretations of "training quality" based on different "perspectives":

According to Le Duc Ngoc, Lam Quang Thiep (2005) - Hanoi National University, the quality of training is assessed by the level of achieving the training goal set out for a training program.

According to Tran Khanh Duc (2004) - an educational development institute, the quality of training is the result of the training process reflected in the characteristics of quality, personality value and labor value. dynamics or professional competence of graduates corresponding to the objectives and training programs of specific occupations. Therefore, improving the quality of training is considered an important task of training institutions in general and colleges in particular.

It can be said: "The quality of training must be reflected in the training objectives and meet as many desires of the stakeholders as possible."

Concepts of training quality:

- Quality is assessed by "input".

Some western countries have the opinion that "The quality of training depends on the quality or number of inputs of the training institution". This view is called "resource view" which means: "Resources" = "Quality".

According to this view, if a school recruits a good student, has a reputable teaching staff, has good facilities ... then it is considered a school with good training quality. This view has ignored the process of organization, management and training taking place very diverse and continuous over a period of time. It is difficult to explain the case of a school having abundant "input" resources but limited output quality or vice versa.

According to this assessment, it is assumed that based on the quality of input resources, the quality of output can be assessed.

- Quality is assessed by "output".

"Output" is the result, is the product of the training process expressed by the competence, professional expertise, proficiency in the job or the ability to provide services of that training institution. There is a view that the "output" of the training process is much more important than the "input".

It can be understood as a result of the training process and is reflected in the qualities, personality values, professional competence of graduates in accordance with the training objectives of each training industry. With the requirements to meet the labor needs of the labor market, the concept of training quality does not only stop at the results of the training process in the school but also must take into account the appropriate level and suitability A person graduated with a labor market such as the rate of employment after graduation, the ability to own and the position of that person in the enterprise.

Quality is assessed by "Value added".

This viewpoint shows that a school has a positive impact and makes a difference of students' intellectual and personality ... that shows that the school has created added value for students. "value added" is determined by the value of "output" minus the value of "input" the result obtained is considered the school's training quality.

This point of view exists only theoretically because it is difficult to design a quantitative uniform measure to assess the quality of "inputs" and "outputs" from which it can be found. to assess the quality of training.

Quality is assessed by "Academic value".

This is a traditional view of many western schools, mainly based on the evaluation of academic experts of the teaching staff in each school in the process of evaluating and recognizing the training quality of school. This means that a school with a team of highly qualified, highly qualified, and prestigious faculty members is considered a high quality school.

The drawback of this view is that, even if academic ability can be objectively assessed, it is difficult to assess the competitions of schools to receive research programs. in a purely academic environment. In addition, it is possible to assess the brainpower of teaching and research staff when there is a tendency to deepen specialization, and the methodology is increasingly diverse. Especially in the field of education today, there are too many secondary schools, colleges and universities, the trend of diversifying professions and training fields; Lack of management as well as poor management capacity in education has made the number of academics owned by the schools increase the quality is also alarming.

Thus, although it is difficult to give a definition of quality in training, researchers also try to find the most common approaches. The basis of these approaches sees quality as a multidimensional concept, with people in different positions having different priorities when considering it. For lecturers, the priority of the concept of training quality must be in the training process, while for learners and employers, their priority on training quality is at the output. , ie the level, capacity, and knowledge of students when graduated ...

From the above points of view, many educational researchers have come up with the concept of training quality as follows:

According to Pham Xuan Thanh (2004): The quality of training is to meet the set goals of the school. The goals in this definition are broadly understood to include the mission, goals, and characteristics of the training program. The objectives must be consistent with the functions, tasks and resources of the school, but at the same time the training objectives must meet the requirements of the country's socio-economic development.

Vocational training law (2006): According to the definition of vocational training goals, the quality of vocational training at the vocational level is the fulfillment of the school's objectives. It is the direct training of technical personnel in production and services with professional practice competence commensurate with the level of training, ethics, professional conscience, discipline sense, industrial working style, and The health aims to create conditions for vocational trainees after graduation to be able to find jobs, create jobs for themselves or study to a higher level, meeting the requirements of the country's industrialization and modernization career.

Vocational Education Law (2014): The general objective of vocational education is to train human resources directly for production, business and services, with the practicing competence corresponding to the training level; have morality, health; professional responsibilities; be creative, adapt to working environment in the context of international integration; ensure the improvement of productivity and labor quality; create conditions for learners after completing the course have the ability to find jobs, create jobs or study to a higher level.

3. Factors affecting training quality

3.1. External factors

The trend of globalization and international integration affects all aspects of the country's social life, including vocational training activities. Globalization and integration require the quality of vocational training of Vietnam to be raised so that the products created meet the requirements of the market, the region and the world. It also creates opportunities for Vietnamese vocational education to quickly access advanced levels.

Scientific and technological development requires workers to catch up promptly and regularly to master new technologies, requiring schools to renovate equipment for research and learning.

The socio-economic development makes the awareness of society and the public about vocational education increasing, learners increasingly affirm their position and role in the cause of industrialization and modernization of the country. Since then, opportunities for attracting investment in vocational education are increasing, schools have conditions to perfect facilities to improve the quality of training. The developed and completed labor market creates a healthy competitive environment for quality training institutions.

State policies and mechanisms greatly influence the development of vocational training in terms of scale, structure and quality of training. The mechanism and policies of the State affecting the quality of vocational training are reflected in the following aspects:

- Encouraging or restraining competition to improve quality. Is creating an equal environment for joint training and development institutions to improve the quality? Encouraging or holding back mobilizing resources to improve quality. Encouraging or limiting training institutions to expand international cooperation.

Policies on investment and finance with vocational training institutions.

Whether or not the standards of training quality. Whether or not the training quality evaluation and evaluation system, training quality management regulations and agencies responsible for supervising vocational training quality accreditation.

Policies on labor, employment and wages of workers after vocational training. Policies for teachers and students at vocational education levels.

Regulations on responsibilities and relationships between training institutions and employers, relations between schools and production facilities.

In summary, the State's policy mechanism affects all stages from the input, the training process and the output of training institutions.

3.2. Internal factors

Training objectives: It is the result, the expected product of the teaching process. The goal of the training or training product is the graduate student with the personality that has been developed and perfected through the teaching process. Learners' personality understands in a simple structure, including: Qualities (qualities of citizens, workers in general, workers in a certain field) and competence (systems of scientific-public knowledge technology, skills - general and specific practices).

Training program: A training program is a system of subjects expressing the training objectives, stipulating standards of knowledge, skills, ethical qualities (attitudes), scope and structure of training contents, training methods and forms, ways of evaluating training results for each subject, discipline and training level of the training level. It is a benchmark for evaluating the quality of training in school units.

The training program must ensure the training objectives and ensure that the design is suitable to both general conditions (framework program) being hardware approved and agreed upon by the superior governing body. In addition, schools have to build software (including discussion hours, field trips, thematic talks), in order to train students in a comprehensive manner in terms of professional knowledge, skills and ethical qualities. Virtues, which emphasize practical competence and a sense of social responsibility, ensure learners are actively learning and experiencing reality.

Teachers play a decisive role in ensuring the quality of training of school units. Teachers impart knowledge, design and organize learner activities, provide guidance and inspire and inspire students' learning. Teachers also have a very important role to play in developing and stimulating students' creativity, helping students to develop career skills and techniques from the time they sit on the school chair.

Article 15 of the Education Law issued by the National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam in 2005 confirms: "Teachers play a decisive role in ensuring the quality of education". This is an important theoretical and practical basis to properly assess the role of teachers in the training process.

The role of a teacher is very important, this is reflected in: Vocational training and teaching, equipped with knowledge, skills guidance, ethics, professional attitudes and qualities that help learners have Be confident when you graduate to meet the demands of the labor market. That is also the basis to assert the position and quality of training of the school in the current conditions if it wants to exist and develop.

Training scale has a great influence on the quality of training. Every year, on the basis of labor market demand, the enrollment quotas will also increase. Besides, to increase the income for teachers of the schools will also increase the scale of training. The increase in training size will result in overcrowding of the class when the school has not arranged enough teachers, teachers will not generalize and can not evaluate the academic performance of each member of the class; not enough equipment for students to practice ... this directly affects the quality of training

Facilities - teaching equipment have an active role in supporting teachers and students to improve the quality of training. The upgrading of facilities, technical equipment is an urgent requirement in the training work in our country today.

The system of facilities for training in each school is an important determinant of training quality. Each training profession requires a system of facilities, but in general, the system of facilities in the school includes: system of theoretical classrooms, practical rooms, libraries, dormitories, equipment for teaching purposes such as textbooks, lesson plans, specialized board systems, lights, multifunction projectors, computers, internet, tables, models, video tapes and discs ... This is a factor. It is very important, indispensable and directly affects the quality of the school's training in addition to other assurance conditions such as teachers, programs, learning materials, etc.

Textbooks are subject materials, through lectures combined with the subject curriculum to help students learn more deeply. Currently, in addition to the reference curriculum, the school also encourages all teachers to participate in teaching writing reference materials for internal circulation. It can be said that the internal circulation curriculum is a standard document because it is a practical result of the school that is crystallized over many years of study.

However, the standard curriculum requires developers to be experienced and qualified. On the other hand, in each academic year, materials must always be revised and supplemented timely to suit the development of the times, in order to constantly improve the quality of training.

The role of businesses in education and training in general and in improving the quality of training in particular is very important. That role is shown in receiving students, internships, businesses participating in the actual report, participating in seminars on curriculum development, training content, cooperation in retraining and retraining. Labor team of the business.

When the school and business have a regular and close relationship, both sides will discover the need for training and solve that need together. In this relationship, the enterprise has a skilled workforce, often fostering professional skills; The school has a source of training and constantly improving the quality of training.

4. International experience and lessons for Vietnam

4.1. China

Up to now, China has issued a relatively complete system of laws and sub-laws related to education, covering many issues, serving as the legal basis for educational management. In which: "Vocational Education Law" was enacted in 2016. Vocational education includes vocational colleges, technical secondary schools, vocational secondary schools, job seeking centers, Social and skills training facility for adults. In order for vocational education to better meet the requirements of economic restructuring and urbanization, the government has redesigned vocational education model, orientation for job hunting, and focused on two educational projects. great careers to meet the increasingly sensitive needs of the society for high quality skilled workers. These projects aim to: 1) create an urgent workforce necessary for modern manufacturing and service industries; and 2) training rural workers to move to working cities.

4.2. Germany and Sweden

Vocational training in Germany and Sweden is based on the basic factors affecting the quality of training. The success of the training process is influenced by factors such as facilities, vocational training programs, teachers and learners. Here, the human factor to implement the teaching and learning process is the most important. The impact of curriculum and teaching methods helps learners be motivated to learn and learn how to learn. Schools without teachers, learners, learning materials can not carry out the training.

According to this model, vocational teachers are given top priority because they play a decisive role in ensuring the quality of training. Teachers not only show their role as instructors of theoretical content and practical skills, but also help learners to realize the importance of careers, create motivation for learning and proper awareness about job.

Also according to this view, the contingent of vocational teachers before carrying out the teaching work is fostered and trained by a teacher training program in a uniform, basic sequence. The criteria for teachers are set out: Teacher knowledge for teaching activities; Teaching methods; Fluent in using teaching aids; Practical experience of teachers, Besides, the level of classroom equipment, types of machinery, teaching facilities also contributed significantly to improving the quality of training.

4.3. In Viet Nam

After 5 years of implementation of the Vocational Training Development Strategy 2011-2020, many important results have been achieved. In particular, enrollment in vocational training in 5 years (2011 - 2015) was 9,171,371 people, reaching 95.5% of the Strategic objectives, an increase of 18% compared to the period of 2006-2010. Particularly for primary vocational training and vocational training for less than 3 months, there are more than 2.4 million rural workers under the scheme of Project 1956. The rate of trained workers at all levels reaches 38.5%, nearly reaching The target of the Strategy (96.2%).

Network of vocational training institutions (CSDN): The number of vocational institutions has increased rapidly over the past 10 years, especially vocational training centers (VTCs). The vocational groups that have been trained by many vocational institutions are those of mechanical engineering technology, electrical and electronic engineering technology and information technology profession ... The planning of vocational training network has changed and Currently, 59 provinces have established vocational colleges, accounting for 92%. Vocational training institutions have financial autonomy, apply information technology in vocational training, manage and develop teachers. By 2015, there were 1,467 vocational training institutions nationwide (including 190 vocational colleges (vocational colleges), 280 vocational secondary schools (vocational secondary schools) and 997 vocational training centers (vocational centers), together with over 40,615 vocational teachers and after 5 years, 7,352 turns of teachers have been trained and fostered vocational skills.

In the context that Vietnam is deeply and deeply integrated with the world, international cooperation on vocational training has been strengthened and implemented at both macro and vocational institutions. and rich, from improving the capacity of policy making, to improving the conditions to ensure vocational training quality of the vocational training system. Vietnam has selected a number of successful countries in vocational training development as its strategic partners, including the Federal Republic of Germany. In recent years, the German Government has actively and effectively supported Vietnam through a number of vocational training projects. However, the integration capacity of the vocational training system in general and vocational institutions in particular is limited; Occupational skills and practicing capacity of Vietnamese workers are still quite a "distance" from developed countries in the region and the world.

5. Conclusion

With the development trend of the market economy, as well as the current globalization trend, the demand for human resources with quality skills and high qualifications is huge. The number of universities, colleges or intermediate schools is increasing. In order to survive and develop in the long run, the labor force training schools for society must focus on the quality of training. Therefore, the quality of training is the most important issue, and it is also a vital issue that determines the existence of all schools and training institutions.

In order to improve the quality of vocational training of schools, the authorities in general need to improve the legal system to ensure the legal corridor and favorable environment for vocational training schools. The Government should soon promulgate documents guiding the implementation of policies on management mechanisms and operation mechanisms in the field of vocational training in accordance with the law in order to facilitate localities in the process of directing and implementing duties. vocational training service. In addition, it is necessary to continue funding according to the annual target program to strengthen vocational training equipment for vocational training institutions.

The Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism and the General Department of Vocational Training under the Ministry of Labor, War Invalids and Social Affairs should continue to invest in vocational training programs and improve the quality of vocational training at colleges. profession. It is necessary to supplement additional budget capital to strengthen vocational training equipment, create conditions for the school to expand its scale and develop training forms and trades.

- Assigning autonomy to schools in training, designing training programs according to credits and orders. (Section 2, Article 34 of the Law on Vocational Education) "The head of the vocational training institution has autonomy and is responsible for organizing the compilation or selection and approval of training programs for educational levels. vocational training ", creating conditions for training institutions to actively build training program). Develop regulations to make the relationship between schools and hiring units, and address-based training. It is necessary to promulgate new standards in quality accreditation for training institutions soon. Expand financial autonomy for schools (decide fee levels, revenues and investment decisions). Create a healthy competitive environment to improve the quality of training of schools.

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